

Trends in Pediatric Palliative Care Research (TPPCR) 2025; Issue #06: Commentary on

Mohanty, A. et al. and Azambuja, D. B. et al.

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Abstract:

This TPPCR commentary discusses the 2025 papers by Mohanty, A. et al., Understanding of Pediatric Palliative Care Among Medical Language Interpreters, Published in Journal of Pain and Symptom Management, and Azambuja, D. B. et al., Culture Humility: Supporting Families with Limited English Proficiency in Pediatric Palliative Care, Published in Journal of Pain and Symptom Management.

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Language concordant care is a key tenet of culturally competent and equitable care. Effective interpretation for families with limited English proficiency is paramount in conversations involving complex medical decisions and psychosocial circumstances – common occurrences in pediatric palliative care. In this month’s reference list, two conference abstracts highlight the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration with medical interpreters in pediatric palliative care.

First, Mohanty et al. conducted a survey-based assessment of Spanish medical interpreters on their clinical experiences, perceptions of end-of-life and advanced care planning conversations, and general understanding of pediatric palliative care. Most survey respondents reported feeling prepared for these conversations (88%) but lacked specific training (65%). Nearly all felt dedicated training would be helpful (94%). Their results also highlighted the importance of pre-sessions and debriefs, and two-thirds of their respondents reported emotional distress after these conversations.

Second, Azambuja et al. provide a case example demonstrating how incorporating a medical interpreter into the interdisciplinary pediatric palliative care team can enhance communication and care. Through pre-meetings and debriefs, they evaluated the appropriateness of specific palliative care language, supporting cultural humility to help establish trust. The inclusion of a dedicated interpreter also provided additional continuity of care.

Both abstracts build upon qualitative work exploring medical interpreters’ experiences in palliative care encounters. In a narrative review, Slusarz (2023) described three roles interpreters

serve: (1) language conduit, (2) cultural broker, and (3) patient advocate. As a language conduit, interpreters translate medical information but can face difficulty in conveying the meaning of complex terms. For instance, Latif et al. (2023) interviewed twenty interpreters across nine languages and identified challenges such as the lack of verbatim translations for “palliative care.” As a cultural broker, interpreters provide teams with cultural context to navigate cultural differences – a role demonstrated in Azambuja et al.’s case, where the interpreter supported cultural humility. Lastly, interpreters serve as patient advocates by alerting teams and families to miscommunication and helping address families’ fears and misconceptions about palliative care.

As a child neurology resident, I have been involved in discussions surrounding diagnosis, management, and prognosis of complex medical conditions, frequently relying on the support of medical interpreters. In one case, our team felt stuck and confused when a family repeatedly declined recommendations for increasing antiseizure medications despite multiple escalations of care for breakthrough seizures. In debriefing an encounter, our interpreter suggested that our approach – presenting different medication choices with risks and benefits to allow for shared decision making and foster patient autonomy – was instead being perceived as an expectation that the medications would not work. For the family, this framing led them to try to avoid additional risk by keeping the previous medication regimen. Here, our interpreter acted as a cultural broker, helping us understand the family's interpretation of medical uncertainty and risk.

In another case, a pre-meeting helped us identify overlapping interpretations of the words “seizure,” “spell,” and “episode,” limiting our ability to draw a clear distinction between electrographic seizures and non-epileptic events associated with a functional neurologic disorder.

Together with the interpreter, we developed a strategy to adjust our word choices to minimize confusion. Here, our interpreter served as both a language conduit and patient advocate, identifying linguistic confusion and proactively suggesting strategies to improve clarity.

With a growing body of literature on medical interpreters in pediatric palliative care, several best practices have emerged. First, pre-sessions and debriefs should be conducted whenever possible¹. Second, careful attention should be paid to language choice, including whether verbatim interpretations exist for terms like “palliative” or “hospice,” and avoiding metaphors or analogies³. Finally, there are opportunities for dedicated training for both interpreters and clinicians on language-concordant serious illness communication³. Ultimately, these findings underscore the importance of a genuinely interdisciplinary approach that fully integrates medical interpreters as essential members of the pediatric palliative care team.

References

1. Mohanty, A., Large, B., Bustamante, I., Shaw, T., & Cuvillo, A. (2025). [Understanding of Pediatric Palliative Care Among Medical Language Interpreters](#). *Journal of Pain & Symptom Management*, 69(5), e603–e604.
2. Azambuja, D. B., Grekov, K., Xenakis, L., & Ullrich, C. (2025). [Culture Humility: Supporting Families With Limited English Proficiency in Pediatric Palliative Care](#). *Journal of Pain and Symptom Management*, 69(5), e708–e709.

3. Latif Z, Makuvire T, Feder SL, et al. [Experiences of Medical Interpreters During Palliative Care Encounter With Limited English Proficiency Patients: A Qualitative Study](#). *J Palliat Med*. 2023 Jun;26 (6):784-789

4. Slusarz C. [The roles and experiences of medical interpreters in palliative care: A narrative review](#). *Palliat Support Care*. 2023 Oct 19:1-8.